

1 **Exploring Mechanism of Corrosion Inhibition of WE43 and AZ31 Alloys by**
2 **Aqueous Molybdate in Hank's Solution by Multisine Impedimetric Monitoring**

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24 **Abstract:**

25 The concept of utilizing multisine dynamic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and
26 distribution of relaxation times analysis to monitor effectiveness of a model molybdate inhibitor
27 for AZ31 and WE43 Mg alloys is proposed. The corrosion kinetics and instantaneous values of
28 inhibition efficiency (*IE*) of molybdate at concentrations up to 150 mM were examined. The
29 inhibitor provides inhibition in Hank's solution at concentrations starting from ca. 25 mM, with
30 the *IE* of about 90%. These data together with results of the surface analysis allowed to propose
31 the mechanism of the corrosion inhibition of AZ31 and WE43 Mg alloys by aqueous molybdate in
32 Hank's solution.

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37 **Keywords:** Magnesium alloy; Molybdate Inhibitor; Multisine electrochemical impedance
38 spectroscopy; Inhibition Mechanism

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41 **Highlights**

- 42 • Effectiveness of molybdate inhibitor in Hank's solution towards AZ31 and WE43 Mg alloys
43 has been examined;
- 44 • Multisine impedance analysis confirmed its usefulness for examination of inhibitor
45 performance;
- 46 • Inhibition effect is provided by a surface film of mixed Mo(V)/Mo(VI) species;
- 47 • A two-stage mechanism of corrosion inhibition of Mg alloys by aqueous molybdate has been
48 proposed.

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51 **1. Introduction**

52 Magnesium alloys combine light weight with favorable mechanical properties,
53 biocompatibility, and osteoconductivity [1,2]. Commercially available Mg alloys, such as AZ31
54 and WE43 are widely examined as promising materials for biomedical applications [3]. In this role,
55 they can be used as temporary implant materials, whose degradation with time allows to avoid
56 additional surgeries, while their degradation products can be absorbed or discharged by the human
57 body [4,5].

58 While the biosafety of Mg alloys has been confirmed in numerous studies [6–8], their
59 practical application is still limited due to their fast degradation rate in physiological environments
60 [9,10]. This causes preliminary loss of mechanical properties and decreases the healing rate of
61 native bone tissue [11]. The corrosion behavior of Mg and its alloys in physiological media is
62 widely reported in the literature [12–17]. One of the ways to efficient corrosion control is the
63 implementation of soluble corrosion inhibitors [18]. Corrosion inhibitors can be used as an
64 individual component of the corrosion protection scheme or in combination with other types of
65 conventional surface treatments, for example, plasma electrolytic oxidation coating, or layered
66 double hydroxide carriers [18–20]. Precipitation and passivation inhibitors can precipitate in the
67 form of insoluble compounds similar to conversion coating, forming a surface protective layer [19].
68 The selection of effective biocompatible inhibitors can be considered a promising strategy to
69 control the degradation profile of Mg alloys in physiological media.

70 In recent literature, the inhibition effect of inorganic oxyanions (molybdate, selenite,
71 permanganate, vanadate, phosphate) in chloride-containing aqueous solutions has been discussed
72 [21–25]. These inhibitors can form a surface protective layer, similar to conversion treatment
73 [19,26]. However, there are no studies of such inhibitors reported in the literature in the biologically
74 relevant media.

75 The typical examination of the corrosion performance of Mg alloys includes
76 electrochemical (linear polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS)) and
77 unpolarized (weight loss, hydrogen evolution, pH monitoring) measurements. However, classical
78 electrochemical methods, such as EIS and potentiodynamic polarization have important limitations
79 in the case of Mg alloys corrosion. In their recent study Wang et al. [27] showed the importance of
80 the system non-stationarity as one of the possible origins of inductive low-frequency EIS response.
81 Moreover, in our recent study [28], we proposed a multisine dynamic impedance spectroscopy
82 (DEIS) as a tool for monitoring non-stationary electrochemical process. We have shown that DEIS
83 in galvanostatic mode coupled with the distribution of relaxation times (DRT) analysis can be
84 effectively utilized for precise real-time monitoring of corrosion processes. Decomposition of the
85 multisine DEIS signal allows obtaining instantaneous impedance spectra and avoiding ambiguities
86 and artifacts associated with changes in the measured system and its impedance characteristics
87 during the measurement in nonstationary conditions [29]. The DRT analysis allowed for an in-
88 depth and precise localization of the number and the kinetics of the ongoing electrochemical
89 processes.

90 Despite being an effective tool in the examination of the corrosion process, the DEIS can
91 be also used to study the kinetics of corrosion inhibition by soluble inhibitors, which was shown
92 for Al alloys [30–32]. Therefore, it is of interest to develop an approach for multisine DEIS
93 impedimetric examination of the inhibitor performance for highly reactive Mg alloys. Moreover,
94 the correlation of the inhibition mechanism with the DRT analysis can bring a better fundamental
95 understanding of the action of a particular inhibitor.

96 In this study, sodium molybdate Na_2MoO_4 was selected as a model inhibitor to evaluate the
97 capability of DEIS monitoring towards examination of the inhibition mechanisms for Mg alloys
98 corrosion. In our previous works [21,22,33] we have showed that soluble molybdates are effective

99 corrosion inhibitors of Al and Mg alloys in NaCl solutions. The inhibitive action of molybdates is
100 associated with the formation of surface Mo mixed-oxide protective layers [19,21,22,33].
101 Moreover, in aqueous NaCl solutions soluble molybdates showed inhibition performance which
102 strongly depends on their concentration [21,22]. The best inhibitor performance was reached in the
103 solutions containing 100–150 mM of the molybdate inhibitor. Therefore, the maximum inhibitor
104 concentration examined in this study (150 mM) was selected based on our previous publications
105 [21,22].

106 Recently, molybdenum has been extensively examined as a biocompatible biodegradable
107 material for medical applications [34,35]. Degradation of metallic Mo proceeds through the
108 formation of surface Mo(IV, V, and VI) oxides, which are later dissolved [36]. Molybdates are not
109 toxic with a high predicted no-effect concentration PNEC of 12.7 mg/L in freshwater and 1.90
110 mg/L in marine environments [37]. The dietary allowance for Mo in the human body is 45 µg/day
111 (0.64 µg/kg/day) for adults [38], while excessive Mo beyond the physiologically normal total
112 values is renally excreted [39], which should allow for metabolic clearance of molybdate released
113 from a degrading surface protective layers without tissue accumulation [40]. For these reasons,
114 molybdates can be considered as a possible alternative for a permanent surface protective coatings
115 of Mg alloys. However, such high concentrations of any inhibitor cannot be used in real biomedical
116 applications. Therefore, the motivation of the present study is to develop a reliable approach for
117 the *in vitro* evaluation of the inhibitor performance for Mg alloys rather than the commercial
118 application of molybdates in biomedical materials.

119 This study aims to examine the usefulness of the combined multisine impedance and DRT
120 analysis to study the kinetics of non-stationary, highly dynamic corrosion of Mg alloys upon its
121 interaction with the corrosion inhibitor. These are important aspects in the provision of reliable
122 maintenance of metallic materials. To do so, we have selected two different types of Mg alloys

123 Mg-Al-Mn (AZ31) and Mg-Y-RE (WE43), and sodium molybdates as the corrosion inhibitor with
124 high effectiveness towards such types of Mg alloys [21,22]. A specific focus is paid to
125 instantaneous impedimetric monitoring of corrosion processes depending on the concentration of
126 an inhibitor and exposure time. A comparison of the obtained data with the results of the multisine
127 impedimetric monitoring of the AZ31 and WE43 alloys in Hank's solution without the molybdate
128 inhibitor allowed for the estimation of the inhibition efficiency. Additionally, scanning electron
129 microscopy (SEM) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were used to
130 elucidate and discuss the mechanism of corrosion inhibition provided by aqueous molybdate in
131 Hank's solution.

132

133 **2. Experimental**

134 **2.1. Materials**

135 Commercially available Mg alloys AZ31 and WE43 were purchased from Smiths High
136 Performance (UK). The chemical composition of the alloys as provided by the supplier is (wt.%)
137 i) AZ31: Al 3.0%, Zn 1.0%, Mn 0.3%, and Mg balance; ii) WE43: Nb 2.2%, Y 3.7%, Zr 0.5%, and
138 Mg balance. The detailed examination of the microstructure of these alloys is provided in our
139 previous contributions and is beyond the scope of the present study [21–23].

140 As-received alloys were cut to samples with sizes $20 \times 20 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$ for electrochemical studies
141 and $10 \times 10 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$ for surface analysis. Before measurements samples were mechanically ground
142 in 99.9% ethanol to avoid their rapid corrosion using emery papers up to P2500-grit without further
143 polishing.

144 Corrosion monitoring was carried out in Hank's solution of the chemical composition (g/L):
145 8.0 NaCl, 0.4 KCl, 0.14 CaCl₂, 0.2 MgSO₄·7H₂O, 0.1 MgCl₂·6H₂O, 0.35 Na₂HPO₄·2H₂O, 0.06
146 KH₂PO₄ and 0.35 NaHCO₃. All the chemicals were purchased from Merck Life Science and

147 ChemPur (Poland) and were of analytical reagent grade. As a source of molybdate ions, Na_2MoO_4
148 $\times 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (≥ 99.5) received from Chemsolute (Th. Geyer Polska, Poland), was used. The solutions
149 containing molybdate ions were stored in closed flasks for at least 24 h under laboratory conditions
150 ($\sim 20^\circ\text{C}$) to ensure equilibration of Mo species.

151

152 **2.2. DEIS measurements**

153 The DEIS electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements were carried out in a
154 three-electrode setup using a BioLogic SP300 potentiostat. The measurements were performed in
155 the galvanostatic mode at $i_{\text{DC}} = 0$ to imitate the open circuit potential (OCP) conditions and assure
156 that no external polarization due to the OCP change will occur during each impedance
157 measurement. The multisinusoidal AC perturbation signal package was composed of elementary
158 sine waves in a frequency range from 22000 Hz to 0.7 Hz with 10 points per decade of frequency.
159 The sampling frequency was 128 kHz. The peak-to-peak amplitude of perturbation signal was
160 chosen to assure that the response signal amplitude would not exceed 15 mV. The frequency
161 interval was selected to ensure the applicability of the DRT analysis. DEIS measurements were
162 performed with a set of PXIe-6124 measurement card (National Instruments, USA) for the
163 generation of AC multisinusoidal perturbation signal and a PXIe-4464 measurement card (National
164 Instruments, USA) for the acquisition of AC/DC response signal. Cards operated in PXI-1073
165 chassis. A detailed description of the used multisine DEIS technique is available elsewhere [29,41–
166 43]. A saturated Ag/AgCl electrode was used as the reference electrode, a Pt mesh was used as the
167 counter electrode, and magnesium alloys were used as the working electrode. The surface area of
168 the working electrode was 0.6 cm^2 . The total volume of the electrolyte was 60 mL. A heating
169 immersion thermostat (Julabo, Germany) was used to maintain a constant temperature of the

170 corrosion medium at $37.0 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$. The fitting of the obtained impedance spectra was performed
171 using fitting software based on the Nelder-Mead algorithm [44].

172 To investigate the mechanism of corrosion inhibition by aqueous molybdates, DEIS spectra
173 were recorded according to the following procedure. First, DEIS spectra of the sample in Hank's
174 solution without the inhibitor were recorded for 10 min. Next, Hank's solution containing sodium
175 molybdate with a concentration of 600 mM was continuously injected into the examined system
176 using a peristaltic pump (Baoding Lead Fluid), using a previously adapted approach [31,45]. The
177 initial volume of the electrolyte was 45 mL and reached 60 mL after the inhibitor immersion. The
178 flow rate was set up in a way to achieve the final concentration of 150 mM of the Na_2MoO_4
179 inhibitor in the electrochemical cell after 50 min (the total time of the measurement was 1 h). The
180 time-concentration profiles of Na_2MoO_4 injection in Hank's solution (Fig. S1 in the supplementary
181 information) were used to calculate the inhibition efficiency. To ensure the homogeneity of the
182 solution, continuous stirring was applied in the case of the measurements with and without the
183 inhibitor. The DRT analysis was proposed to obtain information regarding the charge transfer
184 resistance and protective layer capacitance, due to the inability to adapt a single electric equivalent
185 circuit (EEC) for a dynamically changing corrosive environment and a multitude of processes
186 instantaneously affecting the charge transfer. This study was followed by a 12 h exposure of the
187 Mg alloys in the aforementioned electrolyte to assess the reliability of the corrosion inhibition in
188 time. For the pH monitoring, a Schott Titroline Easy titrator was used. To ensure reproducibility,
189 all electrochemical measurements were at least duplicated. The results reported in this contribution
190 show representative data of the one selected measurement procedure.

191

192 **2.3. DRT analysis**

193 DRT analysis was done with the use of DRTtools software [46] with additional
194 automatization provided by an own-made Python script. Regularization parameter value 1E-7 was
195 used. Resistance values of the processes were acquired by integration of a field under the curve
196 with trapezoidal numerical integration method, also provided by created program.

197

198 **2.4. Physicochemical and surface analysis techniques**

199 The microstructure of the WE43 and AZ31 alloys after exposure to Hank's solution was
200 studied using an FEI Quanta 250 FEG Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) under the accelerating
201 voltage of 20 kV. An Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDX) detector attached to the SEM
202 was used to study the surface chemical composition.

203 High-resolution X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were performed
204 after corrosion experiments using an SES R4000 Gammatdata Scienta hemispherical analyzer. The
205 measurement was performed by a monochromatized AlK α (1486.6 eV) X-ray source with the
206 anode operating at 12 kV and 15 mA. Before measurements samples were sorely rinsed with
207 deionized water and dried in a flow of nitrogen. The survey scans were collected at pass energy of
208 200 eV (with 0.25 eV step) and high-resolution spectra were collected at pass energy of 100 eV
209 (with 25 meV step). The spectra analysis was performed by CasaXPS 2.3.23 software after
210 subtraction of the Shirley-type background and fitting the experimental curve with a combination
211 of Gaussian and Lorentzian lines of variable proportions (70:30). All obtained spectra were charge-
212 corrected to the adventitious carbon C 1s (285.0 eV).

213

214 **3. Results and discussion**

215 Application of the multisine DEIS measurement technique allowed for instantaneous and
216 precise monitoring of the changes in the impedance response of the AZ31 and WE43 alloys in

217 Hank's solution under continuous injection of the molybdate inhibitor. Below, we discuss in detail
218 the DEIS data analysis obtained during inhibitor injection (1 h, coupled with the DRT analysis)
219 followed up by the prolonged corrosion resistance analysis (12 h). Due to the lower dynamics of
220 the prolonged experiment, it was analyzed only by fitting with an electric equivalent circuit.

221
222 **3.1. Corrosion inhibition by aqueous molybdate as a function of inhibitor**
223 **concentration**

224 To quantitatively describe the inhibition efficiency of a corrosion inhibitor, direct comparison
225 of the results of measurements performed in the solutions without and with the inhibitor are
226 required. For this reason, corrosion monitoring was also performed in Hank's solution without the
227 molybdate inhibitor. The detailed description of multisine DEIS impedance spectra in the reference
228 Hank's solution without the inhibitor, their DRT analysis, and discussion of the corrosion
229 mechanism are reported in our previous open access publication [28]. Therefore, in the present
230 study we focus only on the solutions containing the molybdate inhibitor. The reference multisine
231 DEIS impedance spectra of the AZ31 and WE43 Mg alloys obtained during 1 and 12 h of the
232 exposure to Hanks's solution without the inhibitor are presented in Fig. S2 in the Supplementary
233 information. Nyquist plots of the obtained DEIS spectra reveal net-like semicircle with the quality
234 comparable to the traditional methods of impedance measurement.

235 The results of the DEIS measurements for 1 h of the AZ31 and WE43 alloys in Hank's
236 solution containing different amounts of sodium molybdate are shown in Fig. 1 (a, b). At each point
237 of the measurement, the Nyquist spectra display the characteristic, dispersed capacitive loops. It
238 can be seen that the chemistry of the examined Mg alloys to some extent affects the corrosion
239 kinetics, represented by the shape of the impedance spectra, and have a crucial impact on the radii

240 of the Nyquist loops and their evolution in time, especially when the molybdate inhibitor is
 241 gradually added to the solution.

242
 243 **Fig. 1.** Evolution of multisine DEIS spectra of (a, c) AZ31 and (b, d) WE43 Mg alloys as a
 244 function of the concentration of molybdate inhibitor in Hank's solution during 1 h-experiment.
 245 Panels (a, b) represent 3d Nyquist multisine DEIS plots as a function of time and panels (c, d) are
 246 selected 2d Nyquist multisine DEIS plots. (d) Equivalent circuit used for spectra fitting

247 The radii of impedance spectra in Nyquist representation of both examined Mg alloys were
248 observed to increase as the injection of the molybdate inhibitor into Hank's solution began, when
249 compared to the same time intervals in Hank's solution without the inhibitor (Fig. S2 in the
250 Supplementary Information), with the maximum spectra radii upon reaching the concentration of
251 150 mM in the electrochemical cell. This behavior is explained by the blocking effect of the
252 molybdate inhibitor. The obtained results indicate the high effectiveness of the molybdate inhibitor,
253 and that the inhibition mechanism is concentration dependent. At the same time, relatively large
254 concentrations of the inhibitor in the solution are required. This coincides well with our previous
255 data on the corrosion inhibition of the AZ31 and WE43 Mg alloys by aqueous molybdate in 0.05
256 M NaCl solutions [21,22].

257 The obtained multisine impedance data were analyzed by fitting to an equivalent circuit
258 (EEC) shown in Fig. 1e. In the case of Mg alloys, rather complex EECs are usually used for an
259 accurate description of the occurring process [47]. In particular, low-frequency inductive loops
260 should be considered in EECs to minimize the overestimation of the corrosion resistance of the Mg
261 alloys [47]. Furthermore, the value of polarization resistance, R_p , is generally preferable to be
262 analyzed. This approach was utilized in our previous studies of the AZ31 and WE43 alloys [21–
263 23,48]. However, in the case of the DEIS measurements discussed in the present contribution,
264 several limitations should be considered during the data analysis. originating from limiting the
265 perturbation signal in the low-frequency range down to 0.7 Hz. Following these limitations and the
266 shape of the multisine DEIS impedance spectra, a simple modification of the Randles circuit was
267 used. In this circuit, R_s represents the solution resistance, R_{ct} represents the charge transfer
268 resistance, and constant phase element (CPE) represents a capacitive response of the electrical
269 double layer and an absorbed layer to properly introduce the electric heterogeneity of the partially
270 protected electrode surface. The impedance of the CPE can be expressed as:

271
$$Z_{\text{CPE}} = 1 / (Q[j\omega]^n), \quad (1)$$

272 where Q is the CPE constant, j is the imaginary unit, ω is the angular frequency, and n is the CPE
 273 exponent. The exponent n usually describes the degree of the surface heterogeneity.

274 The parameters of the used EEC extracted from the multisine DEIS spectra measured in the
 275 first hour of the experiment are shown in Fig. 2. In this case, each spectrum was obtained at a
 276 different concentration of Na_2MoO_4 in the solution. Since the rate of the inhibitor injection was
 277 kept constant (Fig. S1 in the Supplementary Information) and the time required to obtain each
 278 spectrum depends on the lowest frequency applied (0.7 Hz), it is possible to assign each registered
 279 spectrum to the concentration of the molybdate inhibitor in Hank's solution. Therefore, the fitting
 280 data in Fig. 2 was recalculated to show the parameters of the used EEC as a function of the
 281 molybdate concentration in the solution.

283 **Fig. 2.** Evolution of parameters of the used EEC (Fig. 1e) during 1 h immersion of AZ31 and WE43
 284 Mg alloys in Hank's solution as a function of inhibitor concentration

285

286 The addition of the molybdate inhibitor into Hank's solution resulted in an increase in the
 287 values of the charge transfer resistance R_{ct} , comparing to the results obtained in the same time
 288 frames without the inhibitor (Fig. S3 in the Supplementary Information), proving the formation of
 289 a surface protective layer (Fig. 2a). The highest value of R_{ct} corresponds to the WE43 alloy in
 290 Hank's solution additionally containing ca. 120 mM of the molybdate inhibitor. At relatively high

291 concentrations of the inhibitor (ca. 120–130 mM), a drop in the values of R_{ct} was noted for both
292 AZ31 and WE43 Mg alloys. It is in good accordance with the results of the classical EIS and
293 polarization measurements described in our previous publications [21,22]. This decrease in the
294 surface resistance can be explained by the excessive thickness of the formed molybdate-rich layer
295 on the surface of Mg alloys. This may cause the occurrence of microcracks in the microstructure
296 of the protective layer and its partial delamination from the surface. The change in the parameter
297 Q of the CPE element showed that the CPE constant increased in the case of the WE43 alloy but
298 remained almost constant for the AZ31 alloy (Fig. 2b). The n parameter of the CPE decreased for
299 both alloys (Fig. 2c) as the concentration of the inhibitor in Hank's solution increased.

300 Knowledge about the instantaneous concentration of the molybdate inhibitor in the
301 examined solutions at a given time point and corresponding impedance parameters in the solutions
302 with and without the inhibitor can be used for calculation of the inhibition efficiency, IE , according
303 to the following equation:

$$304 \quad IE = (1 - R_{ct}^0 / R_{ct}) \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

305 where R_{ct}^0 is the charge transfer resistance measured in the solution without an inhibitor. The
306 values of R_{ct}^0 for corrosion of the AZ31 and WE43 Mg alloys in Hank's solution without the
307 inhibitor were taken from our previous study [28] and are shown as Fig. S2 in the Supplementary
308 Information. The calculated values of IE are shown in Fig. 3. It can be seen that IE gradually
309 increases with an increase in the concentration of the inhibitor in Hank's solution. Fluctuations in
310 IE at low inhibitor concentrations are connected with only partial coverage of the surface with the
311 inhibitor and high dynamics of the system. The highest inhibition efficiency varied in the range of
312 80–90% and was higher for the WE43 alloy at concentrations of the molybdate inhibitor above 45
313 mM. Interestingly, the IE of molybdate dropped, especially for the AZ31 alloy, when approaching

314 the highest examined concentration of 150 mM, which is in line with the results obtained for R_{ct}
315 (Fig. 2a). This behavior probably originates from the excessive thickness of the formed inhibitor
316 layer, which may cause microcracks (later observed in SEM images) and delamination of the
317 protective layer [21,49].

318
319 **Fig. 3.** Inhibition effectiveness of aqueous molybdate towards AZ31 and WE43 Mg alloys as a
320 function of molybdate concentration recorded during 1 h immersion in Hank's solution

321
322 To get further inside into the kinetics of the electrochemical processes occurring during
323 corrosion of magnesium alloys in Hank's solution in the presence of the molybdate inhibitor, the
324 distribution of relaxation times (DRT) method was used to analyze the DEIS data. For the first 10
325 min of electrode conditioning, before the corrosion inhibitor injection, the corrosion process of
326 both alloys is represented by a single process, τ_1 , as illustrated in Fig. 4(a, b), in agreement with
327 previous studies [28]. In the initial stage, corrosion proceeds by the dissolution of the Mg matrix.
328 The mechanism of the process can be generally expressed by reactions (3, 4). Fast kinetics of this
329 process consequence in the absence of secondary time constants in the analyzed spectra.

331

332

333

334 **Fig. 4.** Evolution of (a, b) DRT time constants, (c, d) distribution of resistances, and (e, f) calculated335 R_{ct} values for AZ31 (a, c, e) and WE43 (b, d, f) alloys. Vertical dashed line indicates moment of

336 the beginning of the inhibitor injection

337

338 The injection of the corrosion inhibitor significantly complicates the charge transfer at the
339 electrode/electrolyte interface as it is represented by the appearance of at least two additional time
340 constants. This effect is visible from the very first moments, testifying high energy of molybdate
341 ions adsorption toward the Mg alloys surface. These time constants, τ_2 and τ_3 , are several orders of
342 magnitude (approx. 2 and 4, respectively) compared to the initial process τ_1 . Higher times needed
343 to respond to impedimetric perturbation allow concluding the decrease of Mg oxidation kinetics
344 even at low inhibitor concentrations. The appearance of these processes should be interpreted as
345 the growth of the molybdate adsorption layer at the metal surface. Interestingly, the τ_3 process
346 shows high levels of fluctuations, in particular referring to the WE43 alloy. Its origin is speculative,
347 and its appearance might be connected to the secondary processes occurring with the intermetallic
348 particles or the appearance and repassivation of the active-passive cells. Nonetheless, its presence
349 constitutes evidence of system non-stationarity, where proper EEC utilization might be ambiguous.

350 One should also consider that the low-frequency limit utilized in multisine DEIS
351 measurements (0.7 Hz) neglects the direct observation of the diffusion processes or adsorption of
352 corrosion intermediates [21,47] typically seen in low-frequency regimes [27]. At the same time, it
353 allows performing the measurement instantaneously, excluding ambiguities and artifacts and
354 minimizing the error caused by system non-stationarity or the necessity of fitting with EECs.
355 Furthermore, as described by Wysocka et al. [30], dynamic change of the surface coverage, θ , of
356 the Mg alloys by the layer of the inhibitor during the DEIS measurements results in the overlapping
357 of time-constants in the frequency domain and an increase in capacitance dispersion.

358 Resistance of the process can be calculated by integration of a field under a DRT peak.
359 Correspondingly, capacitance can be calculated by dividing resistance value by a corresponding
360 time constant. The resistances (R) of each time-constant are shown in Fig. 4(c, d). The addition of

361 the molybdate inhibitor into Hank's solution resulted in an overall increase in the resistance values.
362 The appearance of two additional time constants, τ_2 and τ_3 , whose resistances surpass this of the
363 process P1 is proof of the formation of a surface protective layer (Fig. 4a). In turn, processes P2
364 and P3 were provisionally assigned to the adsorption of the molybdate ions on the surface and
365 formation of a protective layer of the inhibitor. The charge transfer resistance R_{ct} through the
366 electrode/electrolyte interphase calculated based on the DRT analysis can be evaluated as a sum of
367 the resistances of all three processes P1, P2, and P3 (see Fig. 4e, f).

368

369 **3.2. Corrosion inhibition by aqueous molybdate as a function of exposure time**

370 Further analysis was focused on the long-term (12 h) multisine DEIS measurements, which
371 were performed in Hank's solution on the same samples after the final concentration of the
372 molybdate inhibitor reached 150 mM. The obtained DEIS spectra are shown in Fig. 5. A significant
373 drop in the spectra radii was observed for the AZ31 alloy after ca. 3 h of exposure, while for the
374 WE43 alloy only a small drop was noted after 10 h of the experiment. Fitting of the obtained data
375 was performed using the same equivalent circuit shown in Fig. 1e.

376 The evolution of the circuit parameters in time is presented in Fig. 6. The R_{ct} followed the trend of
377 the spectra radii and was decreasing for the AZ31 alloy for the first 3 h of the experiment and then
378 was gradually increasing. In the case of the WE43 alloy, this parameter was increasing up to 10 h
379 of the experiment, and then started to decrease. The fluctuations of the capacitive parameter Y (Fig.
380 6b), especially for the WE43 alloy indicate instability of the surface passive film, which might be
381 associated with the occurrence of microcracks [21], which results in the initiation of local corrosion
382 attack and the formation of micropits on the surface. The parameter n gradually decreased for both
383 samples (Fig. 6c), yet its values are generally lower in case of the WE43 alloy, which might testify

384 for larger heterogeneities appearing at the surface or layer morphology or the discontinuity of the
 385 adsorbed layer. The latter case is less likely due to high charge transfer resistance offered by this
 386 alloy throughout all the exposure duration. Typically, when n is close to 0.5, the CPE corresponds
 387 to the diffusion process, which might suggest effective surface passivation.
 388

389
 390 **Fig. 5.** Evolution of multisine DEIS spectra of (a, c) AZ31 and (b, d) WE43 Mg alloys as a
 391 function of the exposure time in Hank's solution containing 150 mM of molybdate inhibitor. Panels
 392 (a, b) represent 3d Nyquist multisine DEIS plots as a function of time and panels (c, d) are selected
 393 2d Nyquist multisine DEIS plots
 394

395
 396 **Fig. 6.** Evolution of parameters of the used EEC (Fig. 1e) during 12 h immersion of AZ31 and
 397 WE43 Mg alloys in Hank's solution containing 150 mM of molybdate inhibitor

398
 399 Comparison of the obtained data with the results of the experiments in Hank's solution
 400 without the inhibitor (Fig. S2 in the Supplementary Information) allowed to calculate the values of
 401 *IE*, shown in Fig. 7. The *IE* of aqueous molybdate towards the AZ31 alloy decreased with time and
 402 was fluctuating around the values of 40–60%, while for the WE43 alloy inhibition effectiveness
 403 was much more stable and kept around 80% for ca. 7 h, with further decrease to ca. 60%.

404
 405 **Fig. 7.** Inhibition effectiveness of aqueous molybdate towards AZ31 and WE43 Mg alloys as a
 406 function of time recorded during 12 h immersion in Hank's solution containing 150 mM of
 407 Na_2MoO_4

408

409 Analyzing the impedance data and IE values with prolonged exposure leads to the
410 conclusion that the inhibition efficiency offered by the molybdates remains high and offers a very
411 competitive corrosion protection mechanism. In conclusion, multisine DEIS experiments
412 demonstrate good inhibition efficiency of molybdate toward suppression of corrosion of both the
413 AZ31 and WE43 alloys in Hank's solution.

414

415 **3.3. Post corrosion surface examination**

416 To further examine the mechanism of the corrosion protection of the AZ31 and WE43
417 alloys by aqueous molybdate in Hank's solution, *ex situ* SEM, EDX, and XPS measurements were
418 performed. In this case, additional samples were prepared. To examine the difference in the
419 composition of the surface layers, analyses were performed after 1 and 24 h of exposure to the
420 examined solutions. The 24 h interval was selected to examine prolonged corrosion attack.

421 The surface morphologies of the AZ31 and WE43 alloys after exposure to the examined
422 solutions are shown in Fig. 8. In the case of the AZ31 alloy, a thin passive layer of the inhibitor
423 without visible microcracks was formed on the surface. Line defects seen in the images originate
424 from the grinding procedure. However, no clear sign of corrosion areas was seen in the SEM
425 images after 1 or 24 h of corrosion exposure. The surface morphology was clearly different in the
426 case of the WE43 alloy. Almost the whole surface was covered by a passivating Mo-containing
427 layer already after 1 h of exposure. The surface coverage of the Mo-based layer remained constant
428 after 24 h of exposure. Some spots with larger microcracks in the passivating layer were observed.
429 Such cracks in the passive layer are most probably caused by the internal stress of the layer due to
430 its excessive thickness and evaporation of water from the surface. This feature is well-known for
431 thick surface layers [23,50,51], and was also observed in the case of the AZ31 and WE43 alloys
432 exposed to molybdate-containing NaCl solutions [21,22]. Nevertheless, these microcracks will not

433 result in permanent loss of corrosion protection as inhibitor ions in the solution can form a new
434 protective layer in the areas of the surface defects, as can be seen from the results of the multisine
435 impedance measurements (Fig. 5). Optical images of the surface (Fig. 8) also suggested smaller
436 corrosion attack in the case of the inhibited solution compared to the uninhibited solution (Fig. S4
437 in the Supplementary information).
438

439

440 **Fig. 8.** Surface morphology of the AZ31 and WE43 alloys after 1 and 24 h exposure
441 to Hank's solution with 150 mM of Na_2MoO_4 inhibitor.
442

443 The point EDX analysis of the surface of both alloys showed that the surface layer is
444 primarily composed of Mg, O, and Mo. The content of Mo after 1 h of exposure was 0.9–1.2 and
445 1.4–4.3 wt.% for the AZ31 and WE43 alloys, respectively. After 24 h of corrosion testing in Hank's
446 solution containing 150 mM of the molybdate inhibitor, the content of Mo varied in the range of
447 1.3–3.3 and 1.6–7.4 wt.% for the AZ31 and WE43 alloys, respectively. The relative Mo/O ratio
448 cannot be estimated reliably from the EDX data since the surface layer also contains hydrated Mg
449 compounds with varying stoichiometry [21]. However, EDX data clearly supports the multisine

450 impedance measurements data and confirms that molybdate is able to form a surface layer on the
451 surface of the AZ31 and WE43 alloys.

452 To analyze the chemical state of the surface of the AZ31 and WE43 alloys after short and
453 long-term corrosion experiments, XPS spectra were obtained. The survey XPS spectra of all
454 samples are shown in Fig. S5 in the Supplementary Information. The signals from Mg, O, C, P, Al,
455 Ca, Mo, Cl, and Na were observed in the Al survey spectra. High-resolution XPS spectra of the
456 selected elements are presented in Fig. 9. After 1 h of corrosion, the high-resolution XPS spectra
457 in the energy range corresponding to Mg 1s contained three components (Fig. 9a), which were
458 assigned to the MgO/Mg(OH)₂ surface film (components Mg₍₁₎ at ca. 1304.5 eV (MgO) and Mg₍₂₎
459 at ca. 1301.8 eV (Mg(OH)₂)) and MgCO₃ (component Mg₍₃₎ at ca. 1306.2 eV). After 24 h of
460 corrosion experiments, the component Mg₍₁₎ assigned to the MgO surface film dominated in the
461 Mg 1s spectra.

462 The high-resolution XPS spectra in the energy range corresponding to Mo 3d were
463 deconvoluted into two doublets with the spectrum of the AZ31 alloy after 24 h of corrosion
464 experiments additionally showing the third doublet (Fig. 9b). However, precise peak identification
465 for molybdenum compounds is not so straightforward. In aqueous solutions, molybdenum can form
466 numerous compounds [51,52], with many of them showing the same or very close binding energies.
467 Generally, larger binding energy in XPS measurements corresponds to an increase in the oxidation
468 state of Mo in its compounds. In the case of Mg alloys, it is expected that more than one
469 molybdenum compound is present in the surface layer. Based on this, XPS spectra were employed
470 to assign oxidation states of Mo compounds in the surface passive film. The component Mo₍₁₎ with
471 the 3d_{5/2} peak at 230.7 eV was assigned to Mo(V) compounds, usually observed in the composition
472 of Mo-rich protective surface layers [21,22,33,53]. The Mo₍₂₎ component with the 3d_{5/2} peak at
473 232.6 eV corresponds to the electronic states of Mo(VI) compounds [51,54,55]. In the case of the

474 AZ31 alloy after 24 h of corrosion in Hank's solution, the Mo₍₃₎ component with the 3d_{5/2} peak at
 475 232.0 eV was observed, which was also assigned to the electronic states of Mo(VI). The lower
 476 binding energy of the main Mo component after 24 h of corrosion of the AZ31 alloy compared to
 477 the WE43 alloy may suggest that a mixed Mo(V)-Mo(VI) layer, which was formed on the surface
 478 of the AZ31 alloy has a larger fraction of Mo(V) species.

479
 480 **Fig. 9.** High-resolution XPS spectra in the binding energy range of (a) Mg 1s, (b) Mo
 481 3d, (c) O 1s, (d) C 1s, and (e) P 2p of AZ31 and WE43 Mg alloys after 1 and 24 h of
 482 corrosion in Hank's solution containing 150 mM of Na₂MoO₄
 483

484 The high-resolution XPS spectra in the energy range corresponding to O 1s are of a complex
 485 nature but several distinct features can be observed (Fig. 9c). The component O₍₁₎ located at 531.8

486 eV was assigned to MgO/Mg(OH)₂ and/or CaO [22]. In turn, the component O₍₂₎ was assigned to
487 Mo–O species, MgO, and possibly phosphates [56–58]. Interestingly, the position of this peak was
488 constant (530.8 eV) for all measured samples except of the AZ31 alloy after 24 h of corrosion
489 monitoring (529.8 eV). It indicates the change in the composition of the surface protective film,
490 which is also supported by the XPS data of Mo species, discussed below. The origin of the O₍₃₎ and
491 O₍₄₎ components is not so straightforward. The component O₍₃₎ was assigned to surface carbonates
492 or other components of the Hank's solution, while the component O₍₄₎ was identified as surface
493 oxides originating from IMPs elements.

494 The high-resolution spectra obtained in the C 1s region (Fig. 9d) were deconvoluted into
495 four components with their assignment strongly depending on the exposure time. The first
496 component C₍₁₎ located at 285.0 eV, assigned to C–C/C–H bonds in organic compounds and
497 contaminations [59], was found in all samples. The second component, C₍₂₎, was assigned to single
498 C–O (after 1 h of exposure) and double C=O (after 24 h of exposure) bonding, respectively. The
499 next component, marked as C₍₃₎ located at 289.5 was assigned to carbonates. The last component,
500 C₍₄₎, located at 282.3 eV, originated from the carbides, which might be a surface contamination due
501 to polishing. The components C₍₁₎, C₍₂₎, and C₍₄₎ are mainly associated with surface contamination
502 [60], while carbonates are a part of the surface film of corrosion products [21,22,61].

503 The P 2p spectrum for all samples was deconvoluted into one doublet with P 2p_{3/2} and P
504 2p_{1/2} binding energies of 133.3 and 134.1 eV (marked as P and P', respectively), assigned to
505 phosphates (Fig. 9e) [62].

506

507 **3.4. Mechanism of inhibition**

508 In this section, we summarize the results obtained by multisine impedance, SEM, and XPS
509 analyses and discuss the mechanism of the corrosion inhibition of the AZ31 and WE43 Mg alloys

510 by aqueous molybdate in Hank's solution. First, a brief description of the corrosion mechanisms
511 of the AZ31 and WE43 alloys in Hank's solution without the molybdate inhibitor is required. These
512 mechanisms are in detail discussed in our previous contribution [28] and here we briefly state their
513 main steps. Corrosion of Mg alloys in Hank's solution proceeds rapidly and results in the formation
514 of magnesium hydroxide and hydrogen gas according to Eqs. (3, 4).

515 In the case of Hank's solution, magnesium phosphates and carbonates can also precipitate
516 on the surface of Mg alloys due to the interaction of released Mg^{2+} ions with the components of the
517 corrosion medium. Nevertheless, the initially formed layer of corrosion products is porous and does
518 not provide sufficient corrosion protection of the substrate. The cathodic activity of IMPs in the
519 microstructure of the AZ31 and WE43 alloys [28,63] and the presence of Cl^- ions in Hank's
520 solution result in the occurrence of pitting corrosion [22,28,63]. In the case of the WE43 alloy, the
521 corrosion process has an additional step in the form of filiform corrosion, which initiates on the
522 surface regions of cathodic IMPs [28,64,65].

523 Our results demonstrated that the introduction of Na_2MoO_4 into Hank's solution
524 dramatically changes the corrosion behavior of the AZ31 and WE43 Mg alloys. No pitting or
525 filiform corrosion was observed on the surface based on SEM images. Dissolved molybdate readily
526 retards corrosion attack by forming a protective insoluble film on the metal surface. Importantly,
527 in previous studies in 0.05 M NaCl solutions [21,22], low molybdate concentrations (up to 10 mM)
528 resulted in an increase in the corrosion rate of the AZ31 and WE43 alloys after 30 min of exposure
529 to a corrosive medium due to only partial coverage of the active surface areas. This phenomenon
530 was not observed in the present study for the WE43 alloy, since R_{ct} and IE were gradually
531 increasing with the addition of the inhibitor in Hank's solution (Figs. 2, 3). However, it was
532 confirmed in the case of the AZ31 inhibitor, for which the protection level was generally lower and
533 negative values of IE were observed for concentrations below ca. 15 mM. Therefore, in the

534 discussion below we assume a concentration of the molybdate inhibitor in the system high enough
535 to provide reliable corrosion inhibition.

536 Generally, several types of poly- and monomolybdates can be found in an aqueous solution
537 depending on its pH [33,52]. The change in the pH and the OCP of the studied Mg alloys as a
538 function of time is shown in Fig. S6 in the supplementary information. The initial pH of Hank's
539 solution was in the range of 7.3–7.5 with a maximum bulk pH of ca. 7.9 after 12 h of corrosion
540 monitoring. In these conditions, only monomolybdates MoO_4^{2-} are presented in aqueous solutions.
541 Our multisine DEIS data confirmed that the first stage in the mechanism of the corrosion inhibition
542 is the rapid adsorption of molybdate anions on the surface of the AZ31 and WE43 alloys, resulting
543 in a rapid increase in the charge transfer resistance due to the formation of the surface film. At first,
544 isolated molybdate monomers are adsorbed on the surface. As the bulk concentration of molybdate
545 ions increases, adsorption of excess molybdate would result in the formation of hydrated
546 polymolybdates through condensation reactions of monomers [21].

547 Molybdates have a rather low oxidizing capacity and their aqueous solutions are stable [66].
548 Nevertheless, our XPS data (Fig. 9) confirmed the presence of mixed valence Mo(VI) and Mo(V)
549 species on the top surface layer. Previous studies [21,22,51,66] have shown that this mixed-valence
550 layer is formed in the second stage of inhibition through the reduction of polymerized
551 monomolybdate ions. However, our observations suggest that this stage is greatly affected by the
552 microstructure of the Mg alloys. A thick molybdate-containing passive layer was formed on the
553 surface of the WE43 alloy, while that on the surface of the AZ31 layer was not so thick and did not
554 contain visible defects. It is also confirmed by the difference in the inhibition efficiency, which
555 was lower for the AZ31 alloy. This phenomenon can be explained by the presence of Al in the
556 composition of the AZ31 alloy and its low catalytic activity towards the reduction of molybdenum

557 species. Molybdates could be adsorbed on the surface of Al-rich IMPs. However, the low cathodic
558 activity of Al_2O_3 does not promote the initial reduction of the adsorbed Mo(VI) species, thus the
559 presence of only a thin layer of polymerized Mo(VI) is favorable. These assumptions are also
560 supported by the XPS data after 24 h of corrosion in Hank's solution containing 150 mM of
561 molybdate (Fig. 9), with the relative ratio of Mo(VI)/Mo(V) species on the surface being ca. 11.5/1
562 and 4/1 for the AZ31 and WE43 alloys, respectively. The same behavior was observed in the case
563 of the corrosion inhibition of pure Al and the AA6063 Al alloy by aqueous molybdate [33,67]. This
564 feature is even more prominent in the case of the AZ91 Mg alloy, which contains a larger fraction
565 of Al compared to the AZ31 alloy (not shown in the present contribution).

566 The occurrence of a large number of microcracks in the surface film over the WE43 alloy
567 suggests that the reduction of the inhibitor is not self-limiting. However, active surface sites of this
568 alloy were blocked during the first injection of inhibitor and initial adsorption of monomolybdates.
569 Therefore, no significant effects would be expected due to the further reduction of the surface layer
570 suggesting that initial absorption of monomolybdates and their high concentration in the corrosive
571 medium impart corrosion protection of the WE43 alloy in Hank's solution, providing long-time
572 high inhibition efficiency.

573

574 **4. Conclusions**

575 In this work, the effect of molybdate on the corrosion processes of the AZ31 and WE43
576 magnesium alloys in Hank's solution was examined. The use of the multisine dynamic
577 electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and distribution of relaxation times (DRT) analysis
578 allowed for instantaneous monitoring of the inhibition efficiency in time. The DRT analysis
579 confirmed that the addition of the molybdate inhibitor into Hank's solution resulted in the
580 resistance values and the appearance of two additional processes, assigned to the adsorption of the

581 molybdate ions on the surface and formation of a protective layer of the inhibitor. Electrochemical
582 data revealed that aqueous molybdate leads to a significant decrease in the corrosion rate of the Mg
583 alloys in Hank's solution. High corrosion protection effectiveness of molybdate was correlated
584 with the surface film composition, examined by EDX and XPS. The formed surface film consists
585 of mix-valence Mo(VI)–Mo(V) species. A combination of electrochemical and spectroscopic data
586 allowed to propose the mechanism of the corrosion inhibition by aqueous molybdate based on the
587 adsorption of molybdate anions on the surface of Mg alloys with formation of a Mo(VI)-Mo(V)
588 protective layer, which suppresses further corrosion attack.

589

590 **Declarations of interest**

591 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
592 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

593

594 **Data availability**

595 The raw/processed data required to reproduce the findings of this study are available from
596 the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

597

598 **Acknowledgments**

599 Dzmityr S. Kharytonau gratefully acknowledges financial support from the National
600 Science Centre (Poland) under research Grant Sonatina no. 2021/40/C/ST5/00266. This work was
601 also supported by Gdańsk University of Technology under the Aurum Supporting International
602 Research Team Building – ‘Excellence Initiative – Research University’ (2/2021/IDUB/II.1.3).

603

604

605 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

606

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608 **Jakub Karczewski:** Formal analysis, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – original draft,
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610 **Michał Dominów:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Software, Validation, Visualization,
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612 **Marta Przeźniak-Welenc:** Investigation.

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621

622

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